

Supplementary Material

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Figure S2 Pore distribution of CG₀, CG₀-NH₃-400, CG₀-NH₃-600 and CG₀-NH₃-800 glycerol carbons

Figure S3 Nitrogenous groups (N1 - pyridine and N2 - imine, amine and/or amide) possibly inserted into CG₀ after ammoniation at 400 °C

Figure S4 Nitrogenous groups (N1 - pyridine and N3 - protonated amines, pyrrole, aniline, and/or lactam/peridone) possibly inserted into CG₀ after ammoniation at 600 °C

Figure S5 Variation in the zeta potential of CG₀ and CG₀-NH₃-T according to the pH adjusted by HCl and/or NaOH solutions

Figure S6 Application of the intraparticle diffusion model from the kinetic study (5.0 mg/L; pH= solution; T = 23 °C; Dosage = 2.0 g/L) of CG₀-NH₃-600 and CG₀-NH₃-800

The equations 1 (CG0₁-NH₃-600) and 2 (CG0₁-NH₃-800) present the encoded and reduced quadratic mathematical models that contain the significant terms generated from data processing (Software Design of Experiments) derived from nitrate removal tests established by the face-centered central composite design matrix.

$$\text{Removal (\%)} = +3.22 - 10.37(A) + 8.90(B) - 8.58(AB) + 9.78(A^2) \quad (\text{Equation 1})$$

$$\text{Removal (\%)} = +24.90 - 25.22(A) + 21.12(B) + 18.08 (A^2) \quad (\text{Equation 2})$$

Table S1 Specification of the coded and real levels of the variables evaluated in the Central Composite Face-Centered Design (CCFCD) model planning in nitrate adsorption by CG0₁-NH₃-600 and CG0₁-NH₃-800

Independent variables	(-1)	0	(+1)
Initial concentration nitrate (mg/L) (A)	3.0	16.5	30.0
Dosage (g/L) (B)	0.2	1.1	2.0

Table S2 Matrix of the central composite design of a Central Composite Face-Centered Design (CCFCD) model with response terms (removal %) and the coded and real independent variables of the process for Initial Concentration and Dosage

Trials	Initial nitrate concentration (mg/L) – A	Dosage (g/L) – B	Nitrate removal (%) (CG0 ₁ -NH ₃ -600)	Nitrate removal (%) (CG0 ₁ -NH ₃ -800)
1	-1 (3.0)	1 (2.0)	42.9	88.9
2	0 (16.5)	0 (1.1)	1.8	24.8
3	1(30.0)	1 (2.0)	6.6	33.6
4	0 (16.5)	0 (1.1)	2.7	27.2
5	1 (30.0)	-1 (0.2)	0.9	3.1
6	0 (16.5)	-1 (0.2)	0.2	2.8
7	-1 (3.0)	-1 (0.2)	2.9	34.3
8	1 (30.0)	0 (1.1)	0.4	16.6
9	-1 (3.0)	0 (1.1)	24.3	81.4
10	0 (16.5)	0 (1.1)	3.5	25.3
11	0 (16.5)	1 (2.0)	7.9	44.4

Table S3 Average values of surface area ($S_{B.E.T}$), average diameter and pore volume (PV) of glycerol carbons, obtained through the N₂ adsorption/desorption isotherm

Samples	$S_{B.E.T}$ m ² /g	PV _{micro} (cm ³ /g)	PV _{meso} (cm ³ /g)	PV _{total} (cm ³ /g)	Average pore diameter (nm)
CG0	652	0.26	0.08	0.34	2.1
CG0₁-NH₃-400	558	0.16	0.14	0.30	2.0
CG0₁-NH₃-600	600	0.17	0.14	0.31	2.1
CG0₁-NH₃-800	1034	0.35	0.20	0.55	2.1

Table S4 - Binding energy and its respective attributions and percentage referring to the C1s peaks obtained from high-resolution XPS spectra of glycerol carbons

Samples	C-C (eV)	C-O (eV)	C=N/C-N/C-O (eV)	C=O (eV)	O-C=O (eV)
CG0	284.7 (50.3%)	285.2 (31.6%)	-	-	288.0 (7.3%)
CG0₁-NH₃-400	284.7 (63.4%)	-	285.3 (32.6%)	-	-
CG0₁-NH₃-600	284.7 (73.1%)	-	285.9 (21.9%)	-	-
CG0₁-NH₃-800	284.6 (57.5%)	285.5 (30.1%)	-	287.8 (9.1%)	-

Table S5 Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) values for the results of the central composite design of centered face applied to nitrate adsorption in aqueous medium by CG0₁-NH₃-600

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	Degrees of Freedom	Medium Square	F _{calculated}	p-value
Model	1675.05	4	418.76	28.22	0.0005
A - Initial Concentration (NO ₃ ⁻)	644.81	1	644.81	43.45	0.0006
B - Dosage (adsorbent:solution)	475.26	1	475.26	32.03	0.0013
AB	294.12	1	294.12	19.82	0.0043
A ²	260.86	1	260.86	17.58	0.0057
Residue	89.04	1	14.84		
Lack of fit	87.59	6	21.90	30.27	0.0322
Pure error	1.45	4	0.7233		
Cor total	1764.09	10			

Table S6 Statistical fit for the mathematical model of the CG0₁-NH₃-600 face-centered central composite design

Standard deviation	3.85	R²	0.9495
Average	8.55	R² Adjusted	0.9159
C.V. %	45.03	R² previsto	0.6585
		Adeq Precision	17.9123

Table S7 Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) values for the results of the central composite design of centered face applied to nitrate adsorption in aqueous medium by CG0₁-NH₃-800

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	Degrees of Freedom	Medium Square	F _{calculated}	p-value
Model	7382.60	3	2460.87	41.24	<0.0001
A - Initial Concentration (NO ₃ ⁻)	3815.28	1	3815.28	63.93	<0.0001
B - Dosage (adsorbent:solution)	2675.48	1	2675.48	44.83	0.0003
AB	891.84	1	891.84	14.94	0.0062
A ²	417.75	7	59.68		
Residue	414.54	5	82.91	51.71	0.0191
Lack of fit	3.21	2	1.60		
Cor total	7800.35	10			

Table S8 Statistical adjustment for the mathematical model of the central face-centered composite design of CG0₁-NH₃-800

Standard deviation	7.73	R²	0.9464
Average	34.76	R² ajusted	0.9235
C.V. %	22.22	R² previsto	0.8276
		Adeq Precision	19.8922

Table S9 Parameters referring to Pseudo-first and Pseudo-second order linear models

	Pseudo-first order			R ²	Pseudo-second order		
	Qe exp (mg/g)	Qe (mg/g)	K ₁ (min ⁻¹)		Qe (mg/g)	K ₂ (g/mg.min)	R ²
CG0 ₁ -NH ₃ -600	1.04	0.77	0.005	0.66	1.04	0.306	0.99
CG0 ₁ -NH ₃ -800	2.09	0.86	0.014	0.64	1.97	0.085	0.99

Table S10 - Parameters referring to the Langmuir and Freundlich models obtained from the isotherm of nitrate adsorption in aqueous medium for CG0₁-NH₃-600 and CG0₁-NH₃-800 (pH= 5.5; T= 23 °C; Dosage = 2.0 g/L; 160rpm; 90 min)

	Langmuir			Freundlich				
	Q _e ^{exp} (mg/g)	Q _{máx} (mg/g)	K _L (L/mg)	R _L	R ²	K _f	N	R ²
CG0 ₁ -NH ₃ -600	1.34	1.18	0.21	0.61-0.09	0.97	0.30	2.51	0.94
CG0 ₁ -NH ₃ -800	2.58	2.45	0.45	0.42-0.04	0.92	1.06	4.19	0.97

Figure S1 Ammoniation stage of glycerol carbon (CG0)

Figure S2 Pore distribution of CG0, CG0₁-NH₃-400, CG0₁-NH₃-600 and CG0₁-NH₃-800 glycerol carbons

Figure S3 Nitrogenous groups (N1 - pyridine and N2 - imine, amine and/or amide) possibly inserted into CG0 after ammoniation at 400 °C

Figure S4 Nitrogenous groups (N1 - pyridine and N3 - protonated amines, pyrrole, aniline, and/or lactam/peridone) possibly inserted into CGO after ammoniation at 600 °C

Figure S5 Variation in the zeta potential of CG0 and CG0₁-NH₃-T according to the pH adjusted by HCl and/or NaOH solutions

Figure S6 Application of the intraparticle diffusion model from the kinetic study (5.0 mg/L; pH= solution; T = 23 °C; Dosage = 2.0 g/L) of CG0₁-NH₃-600 and CG0₁-NH₃-800